

The Impact of Price, Sales Promotion, and Service Quality on Purchasing Decisions on the Gofood Application during the Covid-19 Pandemic

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze the factors influencing purchasing decisions on the GoFood application. Price, sales promotion, and service quality were used as the factors tested in this study. The data used in this study is primary data obtained by distributing questionnaires to residents in Depok Maharaja housing during the COVID-19 pandemic. The data used in this study is quantitative data obtained from the results of filling out questionnaires by respondents. This study uses the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) method with a sample that has collected as many as 130 respondents through the Non-Probability Sampling-Purposive Sampling technique. By using Analysis of Moment Structures (AMOS) software, it can be concluded that price has a significant and positive effect on purchasing decisions, sales promotions have a significant and positive effect on purchasing decisions, and service quality has a significant and positive effect on purchasing decisions on the GoFood application in Depok Maharaja housing during the COVID-19 pandemic.

KEYWORDS: price, sales promotion, service quality, and purchasing decisions.

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of technology is growing, especially the advancement of the internet, which is experiencing rapid growth. Data taken from the Databooks website (Pusparisa, 2020) said that there was an increase in smartphone use in Indonesia where more than half of the population in Indonesia as many as 63.3%, used smartphones in 2019 a year later, as many as 70.1% of people used smartphones. As of 2025, at least 89.2% of the population in Indonesia has utilized smartphones. In the six years since 2019, smartphone penetration in the country grew by 25.9%. Moreover, it has been over two years, especially the Indonesian state has experienced a severe problem, namely a problem that attacks the health of the Indonesian people. This is caused by a virus called Corona Virus or what is often referred to as COVID-19. This condition makes the economy in Indonesia decline even, not only in Indonesia but also in various countries around the world. Smartphone use is increasing, so multiple applications appear to make it easier for people in their daily lives, from the emergence of several marketplaces, e-commerce, Online-to-Offline (O2O) E-Commerce such as services on Gojek, Grab, and many more.

According to data from the katadata.com website (2021), the market value of online food delivery services in Indonesia can reach US\$ 16 billion, equivalent to IDR 225.6 trillion in 2025. Based on data taken from the CNN Indonesia

news page (2019) shows that changes in the use of the GoFood application in Indonesia have decreased from 2017 to 2018. However, in 2019 it experienced a significant increase, and in 2020 it underwent a decline again.

Price is something that consumers pay great attention to in everything before making a purchase decision. According to Firman (2020), price is an element of the marketing mix that can generate income for the company through sales. The price set is the best to attract consumers to buy or use the products or services offered.

In addition to price, one of the other variables that food delivery services must pay attention to in selling their services is sales promotion. This is one that consumers highly consider in purchasing food and beverages in the food delivery feature both in GoFood, GrabFood, and ShopeeFood. According to Kotler (2020), promotion is a marketing mix tool with the leading role, namely communication, that has a persuading nature. According to Freddy (2013), promotion is a selling and marketing activity to encourage and inform products of goods and services by influencing consumers to buy products or services offered or produced by the company.

The results of Mutiawati's (2019) research stated that service quality is the ability to provide services serving consumers using goods and services. In food delivery services, sellers offer services such as buying food and drinks

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and directing them to the consumer's location. The data was taken from the Gojek website (Gojek, n.d.). GoFood has been present in 74 cities in Indonesia and already has 550,000 registered merchant partners that offer a variety of food and beverage choices.

A purchase decision is an action taken by a consumer in deciding to buy a particular product or service. Companies need to study consumer behaviour as the embodiment of the entire human soul in their daily lives to get to know consumers. Influence on others and internal motivations will interact to determine the final decision that is considered most appropriate. According to Kotler (2002), "there are five stages in the purchase decision process, namely the introduction of needs, the search for information, the evaluation of alternatives, the purchase decision, and the behaviour after purchase."

Based on several previous studies and the problems above, researchers are interested in conducting research using the object of research, namely consumers who use food delivery services on the GoFood feature Gojek application. Given the current state of the COVID-19 pandemic, which has made people, especially in the Jakarta area, have to stay at home and digital development as it is today has been widely encountered so that consumers can make food and beverage purchases online, primarily through the GoFood feature in the Gojek application.

In addition, this research was conducted because of differences in results or research gaps from previous studies, such as research conducted by Iqbal & Kadir (2019) stating that Service Quality has a partially significant effect on purchasing decisions at Merchant GoFood Festival Duta Mall Banjarmasin. In contrast, Destamar, Aryani & Pusporini's (2021) research states that service quality has no significant effect on purchasing decisions. But a study by Cholili & Rachmi (2020) said that prices and promotions positively and significantly impacted GoFood's purchasing decisions. This is in line with research conducted by Firman Hidayat (2020), which said that prices, promotions, and quality of service had a positive effect on consumers' decisions to use GrabFood services.

This study aims to analyze the Impact of Price, Sales Promotion, and Service Quality on Purchasing Decisions on the GoFood Application During the COVID-19 Pandemic.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Purchasing Decisions

According to Tjiptono (2008), purchasing decision is a process where the buyer knows the problem, finds information about a particular product/service or brand, and evaluates several things from each of these alternatives to solve the problem, leading him to the purchase decision. According to Kotler and Keller (2007), the factors

influencing consumer behaviour are cultural, social, personal, and psychological.

Price

Price is one of the marketing variables that must be considered by company management because the price can directly affect the volume of sales and profits earned by a company (Nasution, 2006). Pricing is the most critical and complex part of marketing management. On the one hand, pricing is a crucial strategic element necessary in the marketing mix because it explains perceptions of quality. Thus it is an essential contributor to product positioning (Setiyaningrum, 2015). Kotler and Armstrong (2008) state that the indicators that characterize the prices used in this study are: price affordability, price competitiveness, price compatibility with product quality, and price compatibility with benefits.

Effect of Price (H1) on Purchasing Decisions

Research conducted by Dival Larkhin Destamar et al. (2021) states that price significantly affects purchasing decisions for users of the GoFood feature Gojek application. The above statement is supported by research conducted by Maburroh, Hidayati, and Hatneny (2020), stating that prices influence the decision to use Gojek. The two opinions above are in line with the research conducted by Cholili and Rachmi (2020), saying that price has a significant effect on GoFood purchasing decisions, supported by research conducted by Firman (2020) and Wahyuni & Hanifah (2022), which says that price has a significant effect on purchasing decisions on BTS Meal MC Donald'S. Thus the research hypothesis is as follows:

H1: It is suspected that the price influences purchasing decisions on the GoFood Application During the Covid-19 Pandemic.

Sales Promotion

According to Joseph et al. (2009), promotion is communicating information between sellers, potential buyers, or other people in the channel to influence attitudes and behaviour. According to Lupiyoadi & Hamdani (2006), promotion is one of the variables in the marketing mix, which is very important for companies to market a product/service. Promotional activities not only function as a communication tool between companies and customers but also as a tool used to influence customers to purchase or use services according to their wishes and needs of customers. According to Kotler and Armstrong (2012), "there are several elements of the main price activities which include price lists, discounts, price discounts, and payment periods." According to Kotler and Keller (2008), indicators of sales promotion are as follows: 1) Product Samples, 2) Coupons or Vouchers, 3) Cash Returns, and 4) Special prices.

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Effect of Sales Promotion (H2) on Purchasing Decisions

According to the research results of Rinalni Cholili and Rachmi (2020), promotions significantly affect GoFood purchasing decisions. The above statement is also supported by Dani Adriansyah and Saputri's research (2020), which states that sales promotions significantly affect purchasing decisions on GoFood in Bandung. And based on the results of the study conducted by Iqbal and Kadir (2019), research states that promotions significantly affect purchasing decisions at GoFood merchants. Thus the research hypothesis is as follows:

H2: It is suspected that sales promotion influences the purchase decision of the GoFood Application During the Covid-19 Pandemic.

Quality of Service

Service quality is a dynamic condition in which there is a relationship between products, services, people, processes, and the environment whose quality assessment is determined when the service is provided (Hardiansyah, 2011). According to Gultom et al. (2014), service quality in a company engaged in the service sector is a fundamental strategy for the success of the company. According to

Zeithmal et al. (2010), the indicators used to measure service quality are: 1) Reliability, 2) Responsiveness, 3) Assurance, 4) Empathy and 5) Tangible.

Effect of Service Quality (H3) on Purchasing Decisions

According to the research results of Iqbal and Kadir (2019), Service Quality has a partially significant effect on purchasing decisions at the Merchant GoFood Festival Duta Mall Banjarmasin. The statement above is also supported by Marissa Christina Edward's research (2020), which states that service quality significantly affects purchasing decisions. The two research results are also supported by the study of Haqi and Rahmatika (2020). Thus the research hypothesis is as follows:

H3: It is suspected that service quality influences the GoFood Application's purchase decision during the Covid-19 Pandemic.

The Framework of the Study

Based on the phenomenon of gaps and research gaps that occur, as well as the many theories and research that have existed before, which are pretty diverse and inconsistent, the authors want to do more research on the impact of prices, promotions, and service quality on purchasing decisions on the GoFood application during the Covid-19 pandemic.

Picture 1
Study Framework

Source: Multiple Sources (2021)

III. RESEARCH METHOD

In this study, researchers used quantitative methods to collect data using questionnaires and test hypotheses. This follows the research problem. The unit of analysis in this study is individuals, namely respondents' perceptions of Price, Sales Promotion, and Service Quality concerning online food purchase decisions on the GoFood application. The population in this study is all consumers who use the GoFood application. The imperious sampling method uses non-probability with purposive sampling with a total sample of 130 respondents. The type or form of data used in this study is primary, namely, data collected by researchers from direct sources and users of the GoFood application. The questionnaire results were collected with AMOS (Analysis of Moment Structures) version 24.

Validity and Reliability Testing uses IBM SPSS Software version 25 by comparing each item's corrected item-total correlation value with a statement with the $r_{count} > r_{table}$. Then, the data is declared valid. A significant relationship occurs if the significance value (P Value) < 0.01 . This test used a trial sample of 100 respondents from a total of 130 respondents, so that the table r value was 0.256 and the significance level (2-tailed) was 100, there was 1% of 0.01. It is known that the validity test results for all items of statements on the variables Price, Sales Promotion, Quality of Service, and Purchase Decisions are declared valid because the calculated r-value obtained by each report is greater than the set table r value of 0.256 and significant (2-tailed) smaller than 0.01.

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Reliability testing has a role in measuring the extent to which the measurements are fixed and consistent. It is known that the value of the obtained variable is more significant than the Value of Cronbach's Alpha yang, which has been set at 0.60, called reliable. Cronbach's Alpha results are variable each: Price of 0.612, Sales Promotion of 0.726, Quality of Service of 0.780, and Purchase Decision of 0.840, so it can be concluded that all the items of the statement on all variables are already reliable.

IV. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION
SEM Assumption Test

An outlier can be detected by looking at the Mahalanobis distance table. In the table, the data is referred to as an outlier if it has a d-squared expensive value exceeding 40,290, i.e., a chi-square value at an accessible degree of 22 (because there are 22 valid indicators analyzed) and a significant level of 0.001. The outlier detection results in the following table show that out of the 130 data analyzed. Seven data had Mahalanobis values above 40,290. This indicates that there is an outlier inside the analyzed data. Outlier data will be output in the analysis using SEM; in table 1 below, the results d of Outlier detection:

Table 1. Outlier Detection in SEM Data
Observations farthest from the centroid (Mahalanobis distance)
(Group number 1)

Observation number	Mahalanobis d-squared	p1	p2
24	33,835	0,051	0,001
73	33,617	0,054	0,001
62	33,299	0,058	0,001
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39	17,964	0,708	0,999
108	17,88	0,713	0,999
33	17,55	0,732	1

Source: AMOS Data Processing Results, 2022

Normality Test and Multicholnearity Test

The normality test results showed that the research data had been distributed normally because the univariate kurtosis value of almost all indicators had been in the interval of $-2.58 < z < 2.58$ and also with a multivariate c.r value of 13.980. The Multicholnearity test is carried out by looking at the correlation value between free variables. The model is declared free from multicollnearity if the correlation value

between these variables is less than 0.9. In this research model, the Co-Branding, Price, and Advertising variables act as free variables. The analysis results in the following table show the absence of multicollnearity among the three free variables because the magnitude of the correlation coefficient between these free variables does not exceed 0.9, so the assumption of the lack of multicollnearity has been fulfilled.

Table 2. Correlations: (Group number 1 - Default model)

			Estimate
Price	<-->	Sales Promotion	0,805
Price	<-->	Quality of Service	0,702
Quality of Service	<-->	Sales Promotion	0,732

Source: AMOS Data Processing Results, 2022

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Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) Test

Table 3. Goodness Of Fit Model Test Results

The goodness of Fit Index	Cut-off Value	Indicator Value	Conclusion
X ² chi-square	Close to 0	292,106	
Significance probability	≥ 0,05	0	Poor Fit
RMSEA	≤ 0,08	0,058	Marginal Fit
GFI	≥ 0,90	0,835	Poor Fit
AGFI	≥ 0,90	0,794	Poor Fit
CMIN/DF	≤ 2,00	1,439	Marginal Fit
TLI	≥ 0,95	0,882	Marginal Fit
CFI	≥ 0,95	0,897	Marginal Fit

Source: AMOS Data Processing Results, 2022

Based on the results of the Goodness of Fit Model test in table 3 above, it can be concluded that 1 *Goodness condition of Fit*

is in a marginal evaluation state and is not good because it has approached the predetermined *cut-off* value.

Table 4. Direct Influence Test Results

Regression Weights: (Group number 1 - Default model)

	Estimate	S.E	C.R	P	Label
<i>Purchasing Decisions <--- Price</i>	0,381	0,104	3,676	***	par_22
<i>Purchasing Decisions <--- sales promotion</i>	0,402	0,166	2,430	0,015	par_23
<i>Purchasing Decisions <--- Service Quality</i>	0,427	0,191	2,231	0,026	par_24

Source: AMOS Data Processing Results, 2022

Hypothesis Test Results 1 (H1)

The p-value of the influence of the Price variable on the Purchasing Decision (H1 -> Kep) of the study results showed a p-value (0.015) < 0.05 with a C.R. of 2.430 > 1.96. It can be concluded that the price has a significant positive effect on the Purchase Decision, meaning that the price offered by GoFood follows the expectations of consumers or GoFood application users. This supports hypothesis 1 (H1) in this accepted study.

Hypothesis Test Results 2 (H2)

The p-value of the influence of the sales promotion variable on the Purchasing Decision (H2 -> Kep) of the study results showed a p-value (0.015) < 0.05 with a C.R. of 2.430 > 1.96. It can be concluded that Sales Promotion has a significant positive effect on Purchasing Decisions, meaning that the sales promotion offered by GoFood follows the expectations of consumers or GoFood application users. This supports hypothesis 2 (H2) in this accepted study.

Hypothesis Test Results 3 (H3)

The p-value of the influence of the Service Quality variable on the Purchasing Decision (H1 -> Kep) of the study results showed a p-value (0.026) < 0.05 with a C.R. of 2.231 > 1.96. It can be concluded that Service Quality has a significant positive effect on Purchasing Decisions, meaning that the services provided by *GoFood* drivers follow consumer expectations. This supports hypothesis 3 (H3) in this accepted study.

Table 5. Variable Causality Test

Variable	Estimate
Price	0,381
Sales Promotion	0,688
Service quality	0,427

Source: Primary Processing Data, 2022

Table 5. Residual Value (Z)

Variable	Estimate
Z	0,638

Source: Primary Processing Data, 2022

Based on the results above, it can be concluded that the Sales Promotion variable has an influence of 0.688 and has the most dominant contribution to the Purchase Decision in the GoFood application. This can be interpreted as the more varied sales promotions provided will affect the increase in purchasing decisions by 0.688 points. This shows that the amount of contribution given by the variables of Price, Sales Promotion, and Service Quality was 63.8%, while the remaining 36.2% of consumer Purchase Decisions in the GoFood application were influenced by other factors outside the variables studied.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

Based on the analysis results using the SEM method, the following conclusions can be obtained: Price significantly affects the Purchase Decision on the GoFood feature. This shows that the more appropriate the price is given, the more it affects the Purchase Decision. At the same time, the selling promotion significantly positively affects the Purchase Decision on the GoFood feature. This shows that the more varied sales promotion provided to consumers will open up opportunities for consumers to increase Purchase Decisions, and Service Quality significantly affects Purchase Decisions in the GoFood feature. This shows that the quality of services can improve consumers' purchasing decisions and open up consumer opportunities in making Purchase Decisions.

Recommendations

Related to the conclusion of all variables, namely Price, Sales Promotion, and Service Quality, it is known that the results obtained significantly affect the Purchase Decision in the GoFood feature. The step that can be done by GoFood is to maintain the price contained in the GoFood feature. The action that must be taken by GoFood is to provide a variety of sales promotions and provide more other advertisements according to what consumers need. The quality of service offered by GoFood, in terms of drivers, applications, and customer service, needs to be improved again. However, the results of this study show that Service Quality has significantly influenced Purchasing Decisions.

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